

Fabrication and properties of magnesium based hybrid composites with graphite nanofibers and alumina short fibers

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SUMMARY

Magnesium based hybrid composites have been developed with graphite nanofiber/alumina short fiber (GNF/ $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_{3\text{sf}}$) hybrid preform by infiltration method. The main objective of the present work is to investigate the effect of higher volume percentage of GNFs with the mechanical properties of the Mg/ $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_{3\text{sf}}$ composite system. SEM analysis shows that GNFs were well dispersed in the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_{3\text{sf}}$ network within the Mg matrix. However, the GNFs were formed agglomerations due to the higher volume percentage of GNF while preforming. Mechanical properties such as hardness, tensile strength and compressive strength of composites improved upto a threshold of 10 VF.% fibers. When the volume fraction of the fiber was above 10 %, the properties showed decreasing trend due to the presence of GNF agglomerations. It would appear that a critical amount of GNF agglomerates may actually be beneficial to the mechanical properties of the composites.

Keywords: Magnesium, Graphite nanofiber, Alumina short fiber, Hybrid composites, Mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, metal matrix composites (MMCs) with nanoscale size reinforcements are typically added to enhance the properties of composites [1]. The principle problem with nanofiber is retaining its integrity and shape while preforming. Hence, the hybrid preform the array of short fibers, which could then be used to disperse the nanofibers in the hybrid short fiber network. In the present research work, magnesium (AM50) based MMCs reinforced by GNFs/ $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_{3\text{sf}}$ hybrid preform with total volume fractions of 10%, 15% and 20% of the fiber were developed and its microstructure and mechanical properties have been investigated. The fabrication of hybrid preform has been described elsewhere [2]. Initially, the hybrid preform was preheated to 400°C while the die was preheated to 300°C. Then, the preform was placed into the die and the molten magnesium was poured into the preheated preform. The pressure applied for infiltration was 10 MPa, and Mg-based hybrid MMCs was successfully fabricated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

SEM micrographs of Mg hybrid MMCs are shown in Fig. 1(a). A good interfacial integrity can be seen between GNF agglomerations and the Mg matrix owing to the absence of debonded regions. The agglomerated GNFs can be viewed as clusters

themselves, but they are present in large numbers. It can also be seen that the nanopores are connected to each other by the GNFs through out the network (Fig. 1(b)). This may strengthen the interface of the GNFs and Mg matrix, thereby improving the mechanical properties of MMCs. Mechanical properties such as hardness, tensile strength and compressive strength of Mg based hybrid MMCs improved upto threshold of 10VF.% of fibers. Above the 10VF.%, it has been found to result in a reduction rather than an improvement in its mechanical properties due to the presence of GNF agglomerations.

Fig.1 (a) SEM image of Mg-GNF/Al₂O_{3sf} MMCs, (b) GNF agglomeration, nanopores are connected by GNF, (c) tensile fracture surface (bonding of GNF and Al₂O_{3sf})

This can lead to a decrease in the hardness. It is also due to the weak shear strength between the Al₂O_{3sf} and Mg matrix metal, which leads to reduction in the strength of the MMCs. The fracture surface the GNF clusters are fully stretched and well bonded with Al₂O_{3sf} within the matrix (Fig.1(c)). It indicates that the GNF cluster contributes well to enhancing the properties of the Mg composite system through the reinforcing effect and also by good bonding of fibers (bridging effect) [3].

CONCLUSIONS

Magnesium based hybrid composites have been developed with graphite nanofiber/alumina short fiber (GNF/Al₂O_{3sf}) hybrid preform by infiltration method. Based on the SEM and EDS analysis, it has been confirmed that the Al₂O_{3sf} and GNFs were well dispersed within the matrix metal. Mechanical properties of Mg based hybrid MMCs improved upto threshold of 10VF.% of fibers. Above 10VF.%, it has been found to result in a reduction rather than an improvement in its mechanical properties due to the presence of GNF agglomerations. The agglomerated GNFs can be viewed as clusters themselves, but they are well dispersed within the Al₂O_{3sf} network of the MMCs. These make GNFs a promising material for micro/nano hybrid metal matrix composites.

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